

A study about the number of Coronavirus breakthrough infections during post vaccination period

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Abstract:

Aim: There are a number of vaccines against SARS CoV-2 used to create immunity belt to reduce the infections, therefore we decided to conduct a study among the vaccinated persons from different countries to find the vaccine effectiveness.

Method: A telephone as well as person meeting were conducted with 30 different vaccinated with the following questions: how many times they vaccinated were, how many times have they gotten the breakthrough infections and how long was this infection.

Results: The analysis indicate that almost all vaccinated persons have breakthrough infection. The airtravel was discovered as one of causes, where some got the breakthrough infections. There were a few fatalities, but the hospitalization was rare. The results do not support the fact that vaccines can provide 95% immunity as claimed in many publications.

Conclusion: The most of vaccinated persons got breakthrough infections of different intensities. It is very clear that vaccination caused immunity were not sufficient to prevent infections, which cause different degree of complications. There is an urgent to improve these vaccines and the question is whether 5th and future dose will be any use in the normal population.

Keywords: Coronavirus, SARS CoV-2, Breakthrough infection, Airtravel, Vaccine, mRNA

Introduction: Since January 2020, there is pandemic outbreak of coronaviruses from a Chinese city called Wuhan. (1-3). Real time PCR is an important method to be used in pandemic outbreak as done in H1N1 outbreak in 2009 but it is shown that approved real time PCR kits for detection of SARS CoV-2 are likely to give questionable results. (4,5)

There are a number of different vaccines being developed and used in different countries. There are a number of research works published about the research work about the effectiveness of some of these vaccines in different settings like different mutation infections in different countries. World health organization has its own website, where it is being discussed how effective these vaccines are. (6) There are contents on website from John Hopkin Hospital, where there are different documents so called briefs showing that the vaccinations are effective up to 95% against the severe form of the infection after 7- and 12-days of post vaccination. (7)

It is shown that there is reduction in effectiveness with the duration of vaccination. Wu et al. published an analysis of data from different publications and showed that there is reduction

in effectiveness over the time against infections, hospitalizations and change in the mortality pattern. It is suggested that other precautions like masks and hygienic measurements are needed to reduce the chances of getting infections. (8). Other groups have also indicated that there is reduction in vaccine effectiveness in different countries like Japan, Qatar, Czech Republic, UK, USA, Hongkong etc. (9-16) The vaccine effectiveness pattern is also studied in the cancer patients. (17) The change in pattern of effectiveness of coronavirus vaccine has been also shown in students. (18)

In this work, we are aiming to find out the vaccine effectiveness in a small group of persons from different countries as well as attempting to point out the duration of illness as well as source of the infections.

Method: In this work, the vaccinated persons from different countries are interviewed in a personal meeting as well as telephone interviews to know whether these vaccinated persons got any infection of SARS CoV-2 after they are vaccinated with starter dose, first dose and second dose. The following questions were asked and noted:

If they got breakthrough infection, how long they remained in bed and which complications have they suffered? It was also asked from where they got the infection and how many times they suffer after the vaccination from breakthrough infection to see whether they have only single infection or multiple infections. The around age and gender were also noted.

The data is compiled in a table to calculate the percentage of different parameters like rate of breakthrough infections, average illness period and rate of complications.

Each person has given a number instead of their person names, so that one cannot identify these persons and their data, hence there is no need of any research ethics committee approval for this research work.

Results: The data is presented in a table 1, where data of interviews of 30 persons is shown. These persons came from Germany, India, USA and Norway. It shows that 27/30 (90%) persons have gotten all 3 doses of vaccinations. None of 30 persons took 3rd booster dose also called 4th dose. The persons used 2 types of vaccinations like vector based and mRNA vaccines. The age of persons took part in this study varies between 18 years to 83 years. The period of illness was between 2 days to 30 days, if the participant got the breakthrough infection. The shortest period of illness was 2 days with light symptoms only in one person, but 27 persons (90%) have duration of illness more than one week. Most of the breakthrough infections show full blown symptoms like coughing, itching throat, pressure on the ears, headache, fever, joint pains and running nose.

13 Persons (43.33%) have multiple infections.

4 persons (4/30=13.30%) got the infection after airtravel. 13 persons (43.33%) got multiple breakthrough infections, out of these these persons, 10 persons got more than two breakthrough infections and 3 were with 2 times. All persons recovered fully; however, 4 vaccinated persons (13.30%) have passed away, but one person got the infection during airtravel on arrival of its travel destination. Two deceased persons have infection too. One deceased person has tumor of unknown origin. The age of decreased persons varies between 50 to 80 years and all were male. 2 deceased persons were hospitalized also, rest

infected persons from this study did not require hospital. The one of the complications of breakthrough infection was activation of auto immune disease leading to alopecia and reduction in the eye sight. Very strong weakness was one of the key complications in some of persons with full blown disease.

Discussion: This is small study, but it is showing one thing very clear that all most every vaccinated got single or multiple breakthrough infections, but the duration varies. This opens the question whether the claims made from the vaccine manufacturers, publications as well as authorities are true that the vaccine is more than 95 % effective. (7) Many publications are indicating that there is reduction of immunity with the time. (8-15) The data shown here is agreement with these publications. Our data is opening the doors to discuss whether to use of a vaccine with such a low immunity. A number of persons got infections while doing the air travel as this is another proof that traveling is one key factor in spreading the viral infection along with the well-known fact air travel also known as transport stress causes immunosuppression, which contribute to get the infections in closed room such as in case of an aeroplane. There is hardly any publication which has studied the effect of airtravel in vaccinated persons. This is a new result, which needs to be studied further and aerospace industry needs to make the travel safer. One simple application is that this industry can use UV-C light robotics to disinfect the aeroplanes to reduce the viral load. Another factor, which may be contributing to increase the spread of infection, it is questionable real time PCR tests being used to test the persons. We have mentioned about such tests in our publication. (5) Even one of fatality mentioned is the data was from a person, who tried to travel as a tourist to Turkey after the vaccination and this person caught infection as he was suffering from an autoimmune disease. On arrival in Turkey, this person got the SARS CoV-2 infection and termination occurred within 5- 6 days. The press created an environment that vaccine is going to be highly effective, but the data in this publication is showing opposite that these vaccines are needed to be improved as many of above-mentioned cases of vaccinated got full blown infections.

It seems that a number of corona virus infections in vaccinated persons lead to complications e.g., loss of hairs and activation of auto immune disease. We are of opinion that some of complications are involving neurological regions e.g., one of vaccinated persons after the recovery of breakthrough caused 2 times car accidents within one week, but this person made never such an accident during the whole life. (data not shown) Similarly other vaccinated person has committed suicide. Such complications need a very careful scientific analysis as these are going to cause burden on the health system. More research is needed here. The regulatory authorities must collect the data of decreased vaccinated persons as many of these incidents are occurring after 6 months or later during post vaccination period. We are of the opinion that these vaccinations with breakthrough infections may cause depression in some cases, but this suspicion needs to be examined thoroughly.

A number of breakthrough cases were treated with Genekampowermolecule successfully as this molecule lead to reduction of the symptoms very quickly. (Data not shown!)

The biggest problem that breakthrough infections are causing complications, hence there is a need of another strategy to prevent the future infection. We are working on such solutions

as it seems that our molecule called Genekampowermolecule is in the position to do this job. This work will be published later.

This work is indicating an urgent to improve the vaccine and another question is that 5th and further dose of the vaccine will be of any use if persons are going to get again breakthrough infections and its complications.

Conclusion: In this work, we shown the data about the effectiveness of corona vaccines as most of vaccinated got the once or multiple infections. Air travel may be a contributing factor for breakthrough infections. A number of complications are shown. The work shows that there is an urgent need to improve the presence vaccines, which do not provide good immunity.

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Table 1: This shows the number of vaccinated persons and their vaccination status along with parameters of breakthrough infections.

Person	First dose	Second dose	Third dose	Infection	Duration (week)	Gender*	Hospitalisation	Fatality	Transport stress
1	+	+	+	Infection	4	F			
2	+	+	+	Infection (multiple)	6	M			
3	+	+	+	Infection (multiple)	4	F			
4	+	+	+	Infection (multiple)	1	F			
5	+	+		unknown		M		Fatality	
6	+	+	+	Infection (multiple)		M		Fatality	
7	+	+	+	Infection	1	M			
8	+	+	+	Infection	4	M			
9	+	+	+	Infection	1	F			Airtravel
10	+	+	+	Infection (multiple)		F			Airtravel
11	+	+	+	Infection (multiple)		F			
12	+	+	+	Infection (multiple)		M			Airtravel
13	+	+	+	Infection (multiple)	3	M			
14	+	+	+	Infection(multiple)	4	F			
15	+	+	+	None		M			
16	+	+	+	Infection	4	M	Hospitalisation	Fatality	
17	+	+		Infection	1	M	Hospitalisation	Fatality	Airtravel
18	+	+	+	Infection	1	F			
19	+	+		Infection(multiple)	2	F			
20	+	+		Infection(multiple)		F			
21	+	+		Infection(multiple)	2	F			
22	+	+	+	Infection	3	F			
23	+	+	+	Infection(multiple)		F			
24	+	+	+	Infection	2	M			
25	+	+	+	Infection	2	F			
26	+	+	+	Infection	1	M			
27	+	+	+	Infection	3	F			
28	+	+	+	Infection	1	M			
29	+	+	+	Infection	3	F			
30	+	+	+	None		M			

* F = Female

* M = Male